

Real-Time Muscle-In-The-Loop Optimization for Physical Rehabilitation with an Active Exoskeleton - A Paradigm Shift

Supplementary Content

1. Terminology of Body Orientation

When describing the body, it is necessary to indicate where one structure is relative to another and the directions in which body parts move. Clear communication on such points requires a universal terminology and frame of reference.

On describing the human body, it is necessary to assume the anatomical position as a reference, i.e., that of a person standing upright with the feet flat on the floor and close together, arms at the sides, and the palms and face directed forward. When the body is in the anatomical reference position, all the anatomical reference planes intersect at a single point, which is called the body's centre of mass or centre of gravity [53].

Many views of the body are based on real or imaginary "slices" called anatomical sections or planes. "Section" implies an actual cut or slice to reveal internal anatomy, whereas "plane" implies an imaginary flat surface passing through the body. The three major anatomical planes are sagittal, frontal, and transverse.

On describing the locations of structures, it is used a set of standard directional terms according to the referential anatomic axis, which assumes that the body is in anatomical position. Most of these terms exist in pairs with opposite meanings: anterior versus posterior, superior versus inferior, medial versus lateral, proximal versus distal, and superficial versus deep. Intermediate directions are often indicated by combinations of these terms. For example, one structure may be described as anterolateral to another (toward the front and side) [49,113].

Supplementary Figure 1.1. Anatomical position, body planes and directional terms [113]

2. Gait Cycle

The gait cycle is usually described as the sequence between the exact same repetitive events of walking. Usually, it is chosen the instant time at which one of the feet contacts the ground to be the initial event of the gait cycle and the cycle continues until the same foot contacts the ground again [47,53,61].

Supplementary Figure 2.1. Schematic summary of the gait cycle of the right leg ([47])

The gait cycle can be divided into two distinct periods: the stance phase and the swing phase. The stance phase occurs when the foot is in contact with the ground and comprises about 60% of the cycle, whereas the swing phase occurs when the foot is in the air and constitutes the remaining fraction (about 40%). Generally, although there are other nomenclatures, the stance phase can be divided into five subphases, such as “heel strike”, “foot flat”, “heel rise”/“mid-stance”, “push-off”/“terminal stance” and “toe-off”/“pre-swing”, whereas in the swing phase it is possible to distinguish three subphases, such as “acceleration”, “toe clearance”, and “deceleration”. These designations are based on the movement of the foot [47,53,61].

Supplementary Figure 2.2. The different subphases of the stance and swing phases ([53])

The contact point of the heel with the ground is not in the centre of the ankle joint but rather offset laterally from it, and it is in part because of that reason that the subtalar joint everts from “heel strike” to “foot flat” – maximal eversion occurs at “foot flat”. Also, during this period occurs internal rotation of the tibia and pronation of the foot, which all together give the foot the flexibility needed to absorb shock and adapt to irregularities in the ground floor surface. Then, the subtalar joint begins to invert – maximal inversion occurs at “toe-off” – and at “heel rise” and “push-off” occurs external rotation of the tibia. The inversion of the subtalar joint and supination of the foot gives the foot the rigidity needed to propel the body forward [47,53,61].

3. Foot and Ankle Joint

3.1. Skeletal Structure of the Foot

Supplementary Figure 3.1. Right foot skeletal structure [49]

3.2. Ligaments of the Ankle Joint

Supplementary Figure 3.2. The Ankle (Talocrural) Joint of the Right Foot [49]

3.3. Muscles Acting on the Foot

Supplementary Figure 3.3. **Muscles of the Leg, Anterior Compartment.** Boldface labels identify muscles belonging to the anterior compartment. (a) Superficial anterior view of the leg. Some muscles of the posterior and lateral compartments are also partially visible. (b–d) Individual muscles of the anterior compartment of the leg and superior aspect of the foot [49].

Supplementary Figure 3.4. Superficial Muscles of the Leg, Posterior Compartment. (a) The gastrocnemius. (b) The soleus, deep to the gastrocnemius and sharing the calcaneal tendon with it. The gastrocnemius and soleus are collectively called the triceps surae [49].

Supplementary Figure 3.5. Deep Muscles of the Leg, Posterior and Lateral Compartments. (a) Muscles deep to the soleus. (b–d) Exposure of some individual deep muscles with the foot plantar flexed (sole facing viewer) [49].

3.4. Ankle Axis and Range of Motion

Supplementary Figure 3.6. Directions of the ankle joint axis: a) Variations in the frontal plane; b) Variations in the transverse plane (adapted from [58]).

4. Neurophysiology of the Muscle

Skeletal muscles have a fasciculated structure. An outer layer covers the whole muscle, called epimysium. Inside it, assemblages of parallel muscle fibres that are assumed to extend to the entire length of the muscle, embedded in endomysium, constitute muscle fascicles. Each one of these fascicles is delimited by the perimysium. These three types of layers of connective tissue have elastic properties and continue beyond the limits of muscle tissue, becoming more collagenous, to form tendons [68].

Supplementary Figure 4.1. Muscle to fascicle to fibre (image credit: openstax.org).

Muscle fibres are stacked in parallel and oriented at an acute angle to the tendon, which can be different of 0 (zero). This angle is called the pennation angle.

Supplementary Figure 4.2. Representation of the pennation angle α between muscle fibres and tendons ([68]).

In the same way that bundles of muscle fibres form fascicles, muscle fibres are composed of myofibrils. These have a series arrangement of basic units called sarcomeres, which are the fundamental structure responsible for muscle contraction. Each sarcomere is composed of a complex of proteins comprised between two dark regions of proteins called Z discs and three bands are visible – A, H and I. The A bands are darker due to the existence of a brew of thick and thin filaments. Each A band includes a central H band which corresponds to the region where only thick filaments are present. Finally, the I band consists of a pale region where there are only thin filaments.

Supplementary Figure 4.3. Muscle fibre to myofibrils (image credit: openstax.org).

Thick filaments are formed by myosin proteins. Anchored to Z discs, thin filaments extend to connect to the myosin complex. These thin filaments are composed of a system of actin, tropomyosin and troponin. Myosin and actin proteins overlap in the A band, with a projection of myosin heads into actin. These projections are known as cross-bridges and their interactions will devise the contraction machinery. Troponin and tropomyosin form a complex that inhibits the binding of actin with the myosin of the thick filaments when significant concentrations calcium ions (Ca^{2+}) are not present. This will impede contraction from happening when not desired. The whole overlapped structure is supported by a framework of titin molecules. During contraction, thick and thin filaments glide without changing length. Only the sarcomere length reduces due to this gliding. Therefore, throughout the whole process, A band length is constant, and H and I lengths shortens [49,68].

Supplementary Figure 4.4. Myofilaments sliding to create force. The zones and bands are represented by each letter – H: H zone, Z: Z disk, M: M line (image credit: openstax.org).

The general mechanism for muscle contraction, known as excitation-contraction coupling, undergoes several stages, commencing with the progress of the action potential from the nervous system to the sarcolemma. When the action potential travelling across the myelinated motor nerve reaches the synaptic bulbs (the motor axon end projections), a small quantity of acetylcholine (ACh), which is a neurotransmitter, is secreted to the synaptic cleft. The ACh combines with its receptors in channels located in the motor endplate, allowing Na^+ ions to diffuse into the sarcoplasm, firing up an action potential in the sarcolemma. Once the action potential occurs, the contractile machinery must be activated. The discharged action potential will cross through the sarcolemma and be widespread across the core of the fibre by the T tubules. This will lead to a release of sizeable quantities of Ca^{2+} from the sarcoplasmic reticulum. Calcium ions will bond to troponin, changing the shape of the troponin-tropomyosin complex and exposing actin double helix bonding sites to myosin cross-bridges [68].

The contraction-relaxion cycle is composed of four main phases [49]:

- **Excitation**, in which a nerve fibre releases ACh, ACh excites the muscle fibre, and a wave of electrical excitation spreads into the sarcoplasm by way of the T tubules:
 1. A nerve signal arrives at the presynaptic terminal;
 2. The synaptic vesicles release ACh, which diffuses across the synaptic cleft and binds to receptors on the sarcolemma of the muscle fibre. This opens ion gates in the sarcolemma, resulting in sodium and potassium movements through the membrane that electrically excite the muscle fibre;
 3. A self-propagating wave of excitation spreads down the length of the fibre and into the T tubules;
- **Excitation-contraction coupling**, consisting of events that link this electrical stimulus to the onset of muscle tension. Excitation of the T tubules induces the sarcoplasmic reticulum (SR) to release calcium ions, and calcium clears the way for the myosin of the thick filaments to bind to the actin of the thin filaments:
 4. Electrical events in the T tubule lead to the opening of calcium gates in the sarcoplasmic reticulum. The SR releases a flood of calcium ions into the cytosol;
 5. Calcium ions bind to troponin molecules in the thin myofilaments. Troponin induces the long tropomyosin molecule to shift position, sinking into the groove between the two F actin filaments and exposing the active sites on the G actin;
 6. Meanwhile, myosin has been “waiting” in a flexed position, like a bent elbow, with a molecule of ATP bound to its head. The head contains an enzyme called myosin ATPase, which breaks down ATP into adenosine diphosphate (ADP) and an inorganic phosphate group (Pi). The energy liberated by this reaction straightens the myosin head into an extended, high-energy “cocked” position;
- **Contraction**, in which the myosin heads repeatedly attach to the thin filaments and pull on them, causing the thin filaments to slide across the thick filaments and shorten the cell;
 7. Myosin forms a link, or cross-bridge, with one of the active sites of actin, and releases the ADP and Pi;
 8. Myosin flexes and tugs on the thin filament, like flexing your elbow to pull in the rope of a boat anchor, and the thin filament slides a short distance along the thick filament. This movement is called the power stroke. Myosin binds a new ATP, lets go of the thin filament, breaks down the ATP, and re-cocks; this is the recovery stroke. Whenever one myosin head lets go of the thin filament, other myosin heads hold on, so the thin filament is never entirely released as long as the muscle is contracting. The myosin heads take turns pulling on the actin filament and letting go;
- **Relaxation**, in which nerve signalling ceases, myosin is once again blocked from binding to actin, and muscle tension subsides.
 9. The first step needed to make muscle fibre relax is to stop stimulating it. The motor neuron stops firing and releasing ACh, so the muscle fibre is no longer electrically excited;
 10. The sarcoplasmic reticulum reabsorbs the calcium ions and stores them until the next time the muscle is stimulated. Without calcium, troponin moves back into the position that blocks the active sites and prevents myosin-actin cross-bridges from forming. Thus, the

muscle can no longer maintain tension. It relaxes, and the action of gravity or an antagonistic muscle at the same joint stretches it back to its resting length.

It is noteworthy that steps 6 through 8 occur repeatedly. The overall effect is that the thin filament slides smoothly alongside the thick filament; this model of muscle contraction is therefore called the sliding filament theory. No myofilaments get shorter during contraction as they merely slide across each other. Since the thin filaments are connected through dystrophin to the sarcolemma and ultimately to the extracellular connective tissue, their sliding shortens the entire cell and its endomysium. If all the myosin heads in a muscle fibre executed a single cycle of power and recovery strokes, the muscle fibre would shorten about 1%. Through repetition of the process, however, a fibre can shorten by as much as 40% [49].

Supplementary Figure 4.5. Main events in muscle contraction and relaxation.

5. Code Implementation

The developed code for the Muscle-in-the-loop plugin is presented in the Supplementary Content repository, inside the folder named "Muscle-in-the-loop Optimization Plugin Code". The online repository can be accessed from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5494470>

This folder includes the following headers (.h files) and the CPP files (.cpp):

- OptimizationMusclePlugin.h;
- OptimizationMusclePlugin.cpp;
- MusclePagmoProblem.h;
- MusclePagmoProblem.cpp;
- SrAndEmg.h.

6. Graphical Results

6.1. Pilot 1

Supplementary Figure 6.1.1. Pilot 1, left ankle results: Parallel relation between SR, EMG, and the SR Fitness.

Supplementary Figure 6.1.2. Pilot 1, left ankle results: Comparison between EMG reference and the online EMG relatively to step count.

Supplementary Figure 6.1.3. Pilot 1, left ankle results: SR evolution in relation to step counting.

6.2. Pilot 2

Supplementary Figure 6.2.1. Pilot 2, left ankle results: Parallel relation between SR, EMG, and the SR Fitness.

Supplementary Figure 6.2.2. Pilot 2, left ankle results: Comparison between EMG reference and the online EMG relatively to step count.

Supplementary Figure 6.2.3. Pilot 2, left ankle results: SR evolution in relation to step counting.

6.3. Pilot 3

Supplementary Figure 6.3.1. Pilot 3, left ankle results: Parallel relation between SR, EMG, and the SR Fitness.

Supplementary Figure 6.3.2. Pilot 3, left ankle results: Comparison between EMG reference and the online EMG relatively to step count.

Supplementary Figure 6.3.3. Pilot 3, left ankle results: SR evolution in relation to step counting.

6.4. Pilot 4

Supplementary Figure 6.4.1. Pilot 4, left ankle results: Parallel relation between SR, EMG, and the SR Fitness.

Supplementary Figure 6.4.2. Pilot 4, left ankle results: Comparison between EMG reference and the online EMG relatively to step count.

Supplementary Figure 6.4.3. Pilot 4, left ankle results: SR evolution in relation to step counting.

6.5. Pilot 5

Supplementary Figure 6.5.1. Pilot 5, right ankle results: Parallel relation between SR, EMG, and the SR Fitness.

Supplementary Figure 6.5.2. Pilot 5, right ankle results: Comparison between EMG reference and the online EMG relatively to step count.

Supplementary Figure 6.5.3. Pilot 5, left ankle results: SR evolution in relation to step counting.

6.6. SOL20

Supplementary Figure 6.6.1. SOL20, left ankle results: Parallel relation between SR, EMG, and the SR Fitness.

Supplementary Figure 6.6.2. SOL20, left ankle results: Comparison between EMG reference and the online EMG relatively to step count.

6.7. **GL30**

Supplementary Figure 6.7.1. GL30, right ankle results: Parallel relation between SR, EMG, and the SR Fitness.

Supplementary Figure 6.7.2. GL30, right ankle results: Comparison between EMG reference and the online EMG relatively to step count.